

ISic0027

I.Sicily inscription 0027

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

sarcophagus

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Panhormus

Place of origin (modern)

Palermo

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 3527

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. D(is) M(anibus)
2. P(ublio) Aelio · P(ubli) · f(ilio)
3. Ver[o] equ[i]tio
4. Rom[an]o [tur]ma
5. prima [qui] v(ixit) · a[n]nis · XII · me (n)s(ibus) · X · d(iebus) · XXII · P(ublius)
Aelius · Felix
7. pater · e[t][---]i[---]oe ma
8. ter f(ilio) · pie[nti]ssim
9. o et dulcissimo et d
10. ulcissimo
11. fecerunt.

Apparatus

Text of

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491787

EDR 137871

EDCS 22000871

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7285 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650790>)

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Tusa, V. 1957. I sarcofagi romani in Sicilia. *Bibliotheca Archaeologica*. Palermo, rev. ed. Rome. At 148 no.70

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